

RM4Health: Remote Monitoring for Elderly (Portuguese Use Case – UC5)

Version 1

Description

This Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the data lifecycle and governance strategies for the RM4Health project's Portuguese use case (UC5), specifically focusing on the remote monitoring of elderly individuals through wearable sensors and smart medication dispensers. It also addresses the management of data collected through interviews with study participants and the assessment of usability and satisfaction of the developed tools by healthcare professionals and caregivers. The goal is to ensure secure, ethical, and FAIR-compliant management of data related to daily activities, health parameters, medication adherence, and patient-caregiver interactions. The DMP defines how data will be collected, processed, stored, shared, and preserved, ensuring compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and promoting the responsible reuse of anonymized datasets for research and innovation.

Funder

COMPETE2030

Grant

COMPETE2030-
FEDER-00391100

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Organizations

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1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [RM4Health: Remote Monitoring for Elderly \(Portuguese Use Case – UC5\)](#)

Description:

This Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the data lifecycle and governance strategies for the RM4Health project's Portuguese use case (UC5), specifically focusing on the remote monitoring of elderly individuals through wearable sensors and smart medication dispensers. It also addresses the management of data collected through interviews with study participants and the assessment of usability and satisfaction of the developed tools by healthcare professionals and caregivers. The goal is to ensure secure, ethical, and FAIR-compliant management of data related to daily activities, health parameters, medication adherence, and patient-caregiver interactions. The DMP defines how data will be collected, processed, stored, shared, and preserved, ensuring compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and promoting the responsible reuse of anonymized datasets for research and innovation.

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [COMPETE2030](#)

Grants: [COMPETE2030-FEDER-00391100](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Data Management Plan

This Data Management Plan (DMP) defines the data governance approach for the RM4Health project's Portuguese use case, which focuses on the remote monitoring of elderly individuals through wearable sensors and a smart medication dispenser. The plan outlines how data related to physiological parameters, daily activities, medication adherence, and patient-caregiver interactions will be collected, processed, stored, protected, and potentially shared. The purpose is to ensure responsible, secure, and high-quality data management practices throughout the project's implementation and evaluation phases. In addition to sensor-based monitoring, the plan also covers the collection and management of qualitative data from semi-structured interviews with older participants and usability and satisfaction assessments conducted with healthcare professionals and caregivers. These complementary data sources will support the iterative refinement of the solution and contribute to a comprehensive evaluation of its impact and acceptability.

Template: [FCT - Template in English](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 DATA INFORMATION

1.1 What existing data will be re-used?

1.1.1 Will you re-use existing data for this project?

No

1.2 What data will be created or produced?

1.2.1 Will new data be created in this project?

Yes

1.2.2 Describe the data you expect your research will generate.

a. Numeric and textual data: Sensor readings (raw PPG, heart rate, SpO2, body temperature, sleep metrics, and step count); Medication intake timestamps and dosage confirmation logs; Device usage logs and system performance metrics; Structured datasets (CSV/JSON) for clinical and behavioral analytics.

b. Image data: Photographs captured by the medication dispenser's camera to verify correct medication intake; Still frames used in computer vision algorithms for gesture or adherence detection. Images from the smart pill dispenser will be used to detect whether compartments are empty or not, allowing assessment of medication adherence against the prescribed schedule.

c. The project includes four groups: Group A (institutionalized elderly), Group B (home-based elderly), Group C (informal caregivers), and Group D (formal caregivers from Santa Casa). Specific questionnaires (CRFs I-IX) will be used to collect demographic, clinical, functional, and behavioral data. Caregivers will also provide feedback on usability through structured interviews.

d. The full list of CRFs used include: CRF I: Sociodemographic CRF II: Personal habits CRF III: Barthel Index CRF IV: Chronic diagnoses CRF V: Health services utilization CRF VI: Medication regimen CRF VII: PSQI-PT (Sleep Quality) CRF VIII: Medication adherence, symptoms CRF IX: EQ-5D (Quality of Life)

1.2.3 Describe the data format you expect your research will generate.

a. CSV (.csv), JSON (.json)

For structured and semi-structured sensor data (e.g., heart rate, activity levels, medication logs). These formats are machine-readable, open, and compatible with most data analysis tools used by both clinicians and data scientists.

b. HL7 FHIR (JSON serialization)

For clinical data exchange and integration with electronic health records (EHRs). FHIR is a recognized healthcare interoperability standard.

c. TXT (.txt)

For system logs, metadata, and annotations. These are lightweight formats ideal for textual data and system-generated records.

d. JPEG (.jpg, .jpeg), PNG (.png)

For images captured by the medication dispenser's camera. These formats are broadly supported and maintain good image quality with acceptable compression.

e. PDF (.pdf)

Source documents from interviews with participants, caregivers, and health professionals.

1.3 What is the data volume?

1.3.1 How much data storage will your project require in total?

100 – 1000 GB

The estimated storage volume of 100–1000 GB is based on the anticipated collection of high-frequency physiological signals from wearable devices (e.g., heart rate, SpO₂, motion data), image data from smart pill dispensers, structured questionnaire responses, system logs, and interview transcripts. Continuous monitoring over several months for multiple participants, combined with the storage of both raw and processed datasets, significantly contributes to the overall data volume. Data will be stored in open, machine-readable formats such as CSV, JSON, and JPEG, which are efficient but still contribute to substantial cumulative size due to the temporal resolution and multimodal nature of the data.

2 DOCUMENTATION AND METADATA

2.1 Documentation

2.1.1 Indicate what documentation will accompany the data.

All datasets generated in the RM4Health Portuguese use case will be accompanied by comprehensive documentation to support interpretation, reuse, and reproducibility. The following types of documentation will be provided: Methodological and Analytical Documentation - Description of data collection procedures (e.g., type and frequency of sensor readings); - Detailed explanation of variables (e.g., units of measurement, value ranges, data types); - Description of

preprocessing, cleaning, and analysis workflows; - Description of algorithms used (e.g., for activity detection or medication verification). Formats and Storage Conventions - A standardized folder structure will be applied across all data types (e.g., /raw/, /processed/, /metadata/, /logs/); - Each dataset or batch will include a README.txt file summarizing its contents, creation date, responsible person, and licensing. - File names will follow a consistent naming convention: patientID_sensorType_YYYYMMDD.csv. Metadata and Version Control - Metadata will be recorded using Dublin Core and schema.org standards; - Versioning will be tracked using a Git-based system or equivalent, especially for scripts, annotations, and structured data; - Major changes to data structure or processing logic will be logged in a CHANGELOG.md file. Additional Documentation - A data dictionary (codebook) describing all variables and field types will be maintained and updated regularly; - Ethics and consent-related documentation will be cross-referenced but stored separately, in compliance with privacy regulations. - All documentation will be centrally indexed and accessible via the project's internal platform, and—when appropriate—publicly available alongside anonymised datasets in open repositories. The data collection protocols will include time-stamped intervals (e.g., daily or weekly questionnaires), interviews at specific time points (e.g., 1, 3, and 6 months), and adaptive frequency in response to clinical events (e.g., medication changes). A Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) has been conducted and shared with the institutional data protection officer (DPO). It includes detailed risk analysis (e.g., data breach, unauthorized access, loss), as well as corresponding mitigation strategies, including physical security, encryption, audit logs, and pseudonymization.

2.2 Metadata

2.2.1 Is there metadata associated with the data?

Yes

2.2.2 Indicate which metadata will be provided to help others identify and discover the data.

To ensure that the data generated in the RM4Health Portuguese use case is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR), the following metadata elements will be provided: Descriptive Metadata (Dublin Core and schema.org) - Title – Name of the dataset or data collection; - Creator(s) – Individuals and institutions responsible for data generation; - Date – Date of data creation and

version; - Description – Summary of data content, purpose, and context; - Keywords – Terms describing the dataset (e.g., elderly, wearable, medication, SpO2); - Identifier – Persistent identifier (e.g., DOI or internal dataset ID); - Language – Language used in textual or annotation content; - License – Usage conditions (e.g., CC BY-NC-SA). Technical Metadata - File format (e.g., CSV, JSON); - Sampling rate (for physiological data); - Sensor type and calibration parameters; - Software version or firmware used in data collection. Administrative and Access Metadata - Access rights – e.g., open, restricted, embargoed; - Data owner and contact point; - Link to informed consent and ethical approval (if applicable); - Version number and change history. Interoperability Metadata - HL7 FHIR resources and references for clinical data; - Mapping of variables to standard terminologies, where applicable (e.g., SNOMED CT, ICD10). All metadata will be recorded in machine-readable formats (JSON-LD, XML) and stored alongside the datasets or embedded within data repositories.

2.2.3 Please identify the metadata standard(s) that apply.

- DataCite Metadata Schema
- schema.org
- Dublin Core
- FHIR (Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources)
- JSON-LD (JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data)

2.2.4 Please identify the controlled vocabularies that apply.

The project will utilize recognized controlled vocabularies and ontologies to ensure consistency, semantic interoperability, and enhanced data discoverability. The following vocabulary will be used, depending on the data type:

Health and Clinical Data

- SNOMED CT (Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine – Clinical Terms)

For standard terminology related to symptoms, conditions, interventions, and observations.

- LOINC (Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes)

For coding laboratory and physiological measurements (e.g., SpO₂, heart rate).

- ICD-10 (International Classification of Diseases)

For classification of medical diagnoses and health conditions.

Sensor and Device Data

- SSN/SOSA (Semantic Sensor Network Ontology)

For describing sensors, observations, and deployments in IoT environments.

2.2.5 Please select the appropriate language for metadata.

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3 STORAGE AND SECURITY OF DATA AND METADATA

3.1 How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?

3.1.1 Describe where the data and metadata will be stored during the project.

Institution networked research storage

3.1.3 Is there a policy in place for data backups during the project?

Yes

Yes, a defined data backup policy is in place during the project. In addition to institutional storage systems, the project uses a cloud-based backup solution with

automated, daily encrypted backups and geographically redundant storage. These backup systems operate in parallel with institutional infrastructure, ensuring data resilience, disaster recovery capacity, and compliance with GDPR and internal data governance protocols. Regular integrity checks and restoration tests are performed to ensure continuity.

3.1.4 Please describe the type of backup.

Full backup

3.1.5 Please describe the frequency of backup.

Daily

3.2 Protection and security of sensitive data

3.2.1 How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

Additional security measures (please specify)

3.2.2 Please specify.

The RM4Health Portuguese use case handles sensitive personal and health-related data, requiring measures beyond the default institutional storage protections. In addition to default security mechanisms, the following additional security measures are in place: - Pseudonymization at the data source - End-to-end encryption during data transmission from devices to the cloud. - Encrypted storage for data at rest. - Role-based access control (RBAC) to restrict access based on user profile (e.g., clinician, data analyst). - Two-factor authentication (2FA) for platform access. - Audit trails and logging for access monitoring and anomaly detection. - Separate storage of consent forms and identification keys, inaccessible from the main dataset. - Physical access to paper records is restricted and locked. - Computers storing personal data are password-protected and encrypted. - Backup disks are encrypted and stored securely, with limited access. - No data copies are allowed outside of approved storage. - Risks identified: unauthorized access (e.g., hacking, physical theft), transcription errors, accidental deletion.

4 PERSONAL DATA, INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS AND OWNERSHIP

4.1 How will you handle issues regarding the processing of personal information and intellectual property rights and ownership?

4.1.1 Will you process and/or store personal data during your project?

Yes

4.1.2 How will compliance with legislation and (institutional) regulation on personal data be ensured?

The RM4Health Portuguese use case will process and store personal and health-related data from elderly participants, including physiological signals (e.g., heart rate, SpO₂), activity patterns, medication intake logs, and patient-caregiver interactions. Although all data will be pseudonymised at the point of collection, it still qualifies as personal data under GDPR, as re-identification could occur if combined with other information. Appropriate legal, ethical, and technical safeguards are in place, including: - Informed consent; - Ethics committee approval; - GDPR-compliant data processing agreements; - Restricted access, encryption, and audit trails.

4.1.3 How will ownership of the data and intellectual property rights to the data be managed?

Ownership of the data generated in the Portuguese use case of the RM4Health project will be shared among the institutional partners directly involved in data collection, processing, and analysis. Specifically, raw and processed data collected through wearable sensors, smart medication dispensers, interviews with elderly participants, questionnaires, and usability evaluations with healthcare professionals and caregivers will be jointly owned by ISEP (Instituto Superior de Engenharia do Porto), Santa Casa da Misericórdia do Porto, and Wiseware, the leading company responsible for the development of the monitoring devices. The Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto (FMUP) will participate in the data analysis phase. FMUP will have access exclusively to de-identified datasets derived from sensor data, interview transcripts, and participant questionnaires, strictly for research and evaluation purposes. No personally identifiable information will be shared with FMUP, ensuring compliance with ethical and data protection standards. Each partner will have the right to access and use the data they generate or contribute to, in accordance with the data sharing and collaboration

agreements established within the consortium. Intellectual property (IP) rights over derived results, such as algorithms, software components, and analytical frameworks, will be governed by the RM4Health consortium agreement, which specifies conditions for exploitation, publication, and licensing. Access to the data will be controlled by designated data stewards at each institution, in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and internal ethical protocols. For research purposes, only de-identified and anonymized datasets will be made available to external parties, upon approval by the project's data governance board and under data sharing agreements that ensure the protection of participant privacy and institutional rights.

5 DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION

5.1 Long-term data preservation

5.1.1 How will data be selected for long-term preservation?

All data resulting from the project will be preserved for at least 10 years

5.2 Data available for re-use

5.2.1 What data will be made available for re-use?

All data resulting from the project will be made available

5.2.3 When will the data be available for re-use, and for how long will the data be available?

Data available as soon as article is published

The RM4Health Portuguese use case will make data available for re-use upon publication of peer-reviewed articles that rely on the respective datasets. This ensures timely data sharing aligned with funding agency requirements, while also allowing researchers to prepare and validate the data for responsible release. **Timely Release:** Data will be released in parallel with each associated publication, ensuring that other researchers can access the underlying data upon reading the results. **Duration of Availability:** The data will remain available indefinitely, hosted in certified repositories (e.g., Zenodo, institutional platforms) with persistent identifiers (e.g., DOI) to support long-term access. **Restrictions & Embargoes:** In cases involving sensitive health data or pending intellectual property (e.g., novel algorithms), access may be restricted to anonymized aggregates or delayed with a short embargo (≤ 6 months) to ensure compliance with ethical approvals and

publication strategy. Exclusive Use: No long-term exclusive use will be claimed. Temporary restrictions may apply only until publication or validation of findings, as per standard academic practice.

5.2.4 In which repository will the data be archived and made available for re-use, and under which license?

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Zenodo

5.2.5 Please confirm if:

The repository is certified

5.2.6 Please indicate whether a persistent identifier will be pursued.

Yes

- DOI
- PURL
- URL

5.2.7 Under which license will the data be archived and made available for re-use?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

5.2.8 Describe your strategy for publishing the analysis software that will be generated in this project.

No need for specific tools or software. Raw data will be provided in standards formats.

6 RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES

6.1 Responsibilities and resources for data management

6.1.1 Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management?

- Filipe Andrade Bernardi (orcid: [0000-0002-9597-5470](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9597-5470))
- Vinicius Costa Lima (orcid: [0000-0002-2467-358X](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2467-358X))

Faculdade de Medicina da Universidade do Porto (FMUP)

- ISEP: Hosts servers and manages the integration of data from devices, system interfaces, and questionnaires - FMUP: Leads research and analysis; accesses only pseudonymized data - Santa Casa da Misericórdia de Vagos: Handles recruitment and data collection at the local level WISEWARE: Develops hardware and communication infrastructure; no access to sensitive data

6.1.2 What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)?

The RM4Health Portuguese use case has allocated dedicated resources to ensure that all data generated complies with FAIR principles. This includes staff time for data curation, anonymization, metadata creation, and repository preparation. The project leverages institutional network infrastructure for storage and backups. The dissemination and data management lines cover repository-related tasks, including documentation, metadata standardization, and long-term deposit. No significant additional costs are expected, as the project relies on open-source tools and free, certified repositories.

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